

Rice yield and release of iron in soil as influenced by presowing soil water treatments and coating seed with iron compounds at Rahuri, India.

Treatment	Rice yield (t/ha)		Release of iron in soil (ppm)						
	Grain	Straw	Water treatment before sowing		Sowing	Tillering	Panicle initiation	Flowering	Harvest
			1 day	15 days					
Water treatment									
Control	2.1	2.4	1.64	1.64	2.64	2.91	2.88	2.60	1.71
Soil saturation	2.3	2.7	1.72	3.73	3.77	3.16	3.06	3.08	1.98
Seed coating									
Control	2.1	2.4	—	—	3.18	3.06	2.96	2.79	1.84
FeSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	2.2	2.6	—	—	3.20	2.97	2.85	2.85	1.97
Fe EDTA	2.2	2.6	—	—	3.24	3.01	2.98	2.89	1.71
Water treatment									
F-test	**	**	ns	**	**	**	**	**	ns
S.E. ±	0.21	0.17	0.06	0.04	0.05	0.02	0.02	0.05	0.09
C.D. at 5%	0.63	0.51	—	0.12	0.14	0.07	0.07	0.15	—
Seed coating									
F-test	**	**	—	—	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns
S.E. ±	0.25	0.21	—	—	0.06	0.03	0.03	0.06	0.12
C.D. at 5%	0.75	0.63	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Interaction									
F-test	**	**	—	—	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns

cantly higher under the presowing soil saturation treatment. This might be due to the increased availability of Fe.

Coating seed with FeSO₄·7H₂O and

Fe EDTA significantly increased yield, probably because of the increased availability of Fe to rice plants. The interaction between presowing soil water

treatment and coating seed with Fe compounds significantly increased yield. ■

Urea application and time of incorporation in Bangladesh paddy

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Urea fertilizer usually is incorporated into paddy soil soon after application. But urea is not well absorbed by soil particles in ill-drained paddy fields with deep standing water. A large portion remains in the standing water, even after intensive incorporation practices. The unincorporated urea may be lost through volatilization and denitrification. Because ammonium is easily absorbed by soil particles, incorporation a few days after urea application, after a major portion has been ammonified, may increase the effect of the fertilizer.

A first trial on soil incubation showed that the highest amount of exchangeable ammonium remained in the soil with incorporation 2 to 4 days after urea application (Table 1). In a field trial using 253-m² plots in 1981 T. aman season, incorporation 4 days after application maximized paddy yields (Table 2). ■

Table 1. Effect of incorporation lag on recovery of urea^a nitrogen after 17-day incubation in Bangladesh.

Incorporation (days after application)	Oxidative layer (mm)	Ammonium nitrogen (ppm)
0	6.8	74
2	6.6	103
4	6.5	102
6	6.0	93
9	5.2	76
No incorporation	9.8	70

^aRate of 40 kg N/ha, 5 cm standing water, extracted soil layer 5 cm.

Effect of insecticide application on nitrogen transformation in flooded soil

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A soil incubation experiment studied the effects of soil-applied insecticides such as lindane, carbofuran, FMC 35001, and the herbicide butachlor on nitrogen (N) transformations in flooded fields at Coimbatore. The soil was a moderately drained, deep clay loam with a pH of 7.5 and low available N. Pesticides were applied at field dosage. The soil was

Table 2. Effect of time of soil incorporation of applied urea on paddy yield in Bangladesh.^a

Incorporation (days after application)	Paddy yield (t/ha)
0	5.0
1	5.0
2	5.3
3	6.7
4	6.6
5	6.5

^aBR 10 variety, 3-split application (40-20-20 kg N/ha).

kept flooded. NH₄-N, NO₃-N, and NO₂-N were determined at different stages of incubation. A completely randomized block design was replicated four times.

Application of lindane and butachlor resulted in lower levels of nitrites and nitrates 2 days after application (see table). Later, the reduction was not significant. A higher accumulation of NH₄-N appeared at early stages but later the NH₄-N was nitrified into NO₂ and NO₃.

Lindane and butachlor seem to be slightly inhibitory to some nitrifying microorganisms, slowing down the nitrification reaction for about 2 days. This effect slowly disappeared and was not felt after 5 days. ■